

INDISCIPLINARY USE OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS TO WORK TRADITIONS PSYCHOLOGICAL PREPARATION CONDITIONS

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Annotation: In the article, in the psychological preparation of elementary school students for work, showing pictures of people's labor heroes in places where it is possible, organizing meetings and discussion nights with them, and holding them, will give a good result to arouse the desire of students to show themselves in work, and also to introduce elementary school students to labor traditions. written on the conditions of psychological preparation for interdisciplinary use.

Key words: Primary school students, work education, psychological preparation for work, work tasks, diligence

Psychological preparation of elementary school students for work involves influencing their emotions, not their mind and will. Fiction and art play a positive role in this. In the psychological preparation of elementary school students for work, showing pictures of people's labor heroes in places where possible, organizing meetings and discussion evenings with them and holding them will give a good result, in order to arouse the desire of students to show themselves in work.

For this purpose, it is necessary to use artistic and documentary films, TV shows dedicated to science and technology news, newspaper-magazine articles, and hold debates and question-and-answer evenings in order to strengthen their influence. It is known that the behavior of elementary school students is influenced not only by what is perceived, but also by what is thought and felt. The essence and means of psychological preparation of elementary school students for work, in order to achieve the effectiveness of work, it is necessary to achieve a clear and clear embodiment of the image of what is created due to work in their minds.

Regardless of whether the work is simple or complex, the goals and tasks of work should be clearly explained to primary school students. In order for elementary school students to understand the results of work, the first condition for psychological preparation for work is to teach them from a young age to understand the goals and tasks of their future work. The work experiences of primary school students are getting wider and deeper. They clearly understand the role of work in personal and social life, and realize its necessity and importance. Adolescence, especially in youth, is about understanding the role and importance of work.

The first buds of work activity of elementary school students are manifested in their interest in the work of high school students and their desire to participate in it. Achievements in the performance of work tasks will gradually change the passionate attitude to work, help to better understand its place in the life of the whole society and every person, and the demands placed on work by each person. Communication was introduced into the form of

friendship on the basis of mutual trust and equal rights relations: the older one fulfills the role of a friend and offers the younger one to fulfill the same role. The friendly form of communication reflects the attitude of partners in work, in which the elder gives the younger the relevant information, expresses his respect for him, does not demand that he follow him. But he believes that the strength of the relationship between the elder and the younger is that even when they are separated, their desires and interests will be compatible.

The educational possibilities of friendly communication at work are based on the personal influence of adults on children, on the conscious targeting of voluntary fulfillment of their wishes by children, and trust in them. In this form of communication, methods of influence such as discussion, advice, persuasion, request, and encouragement are acceptable. Psychological preparation of elementary school students for work is based on raising them in the spirit of respect for any work necessary for society, regardless of whether it is physical or mental, complex or simple. The idea that working is never a shame, and at the same time, a person is always happy with his work, should be inculcated in the minds of the young generation.

In order to prepare primary school students for their future work, it is important to organize their work throughout the school year. The earlier the formation of working skills, skills and competences in elementary school students begins, the faster they are formed. A necessary condition for the introduction of labor education classes in the elementary grades is that when working in the workshop and in the fields, students will be satisfied with their work only when they realize that the things they have made with their own hands are useful to themselves and others.

One of the important means of achieving success in labor education is the suitability of labor tools, equipment and labor standards to the age and specific characteristics of students. It does not take long observation to prove this. Working with heavy hammers, long saws and hacksaws, large shears, shovels and hoes quickly tires elementary school students. Students who do not achieve the desired results lose their desire to work. In such working conditions, when new assignments are given, students tend to refuse to complete them. There is no need to prove that work tasks can be completed only if the tools are suitable for the age and gender of the elementary school student.

Some materials (hard types of wood, thick cardboard, etc.) are processed with great difficulty and the work does not work. Because of this, primary school students lose their enthusiasm for work. Exaggeration of labor standards leads to a cold attitude towards labor. Unfortunately, it is no secret that not enough research has been conducted on the problems of psychology and physiology of work of elementary school students. Teachers are forced to work on the basis of their pedagogical experience and observation of students' work in providing work education to primary school students.

The right way to achieve success in labor education is its ideological approach. He should form the right attitude to work in elementary school students. Therefore, primary school students should not only understand the tasks set before them, but should actively participate in the performance of this task with their work in accordance with their age characteristics.

In our people, the power of words is compared to an atomic bomb. In fact, if a serious conversation is held with a person about his shortcomings, he will gradually or quickly lose

his shortcomings. In particular, oral explanation and persuasion play the following three roles in the student's life:

- a) if persuasion and explanation can be proved, it arouses in the student the need to change his behavior and shows ways of self-education;
- b) oral explanation and persuasion shows the student's achievements and shortcomings in the course of his work by correcting, punishing and admonishing;
- c) finally, they strengthen the good results caused by the change of the student's behavior, determine the ways to develop the necessary qualities.

However, no matter how good the verbal influence is, it alone will not produce the desired result. Perhaps any quality of the student's personality is formed only as a result of repeatedly performed actions, is formed in the activity.

Therefore, human behavior consists of a set of personal qualities that express specific behaviors, and it consists of dynamic stereotypes, which are manifested in personal qualities, activities and actions. If the student is not taught to be truthful and honest, then honesty and integrity cannot be cultivated. If the student does not show himself in work, then it will be difficult to educate hard work..

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